

Production of biodiesel by esterification reaction of lipids extracted from Duckweed plants

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Abstract: Providing renewable energy sources concerns scholars throughout the world. The current study aimed to investigate low-cost biomass feedstock for biodiesel production, and the duckweed plant was utilised for this purpose. The extraction process was accomplished by immersing the dried feedstock in a mixture of chloroform and methanol (2:1). The extraction process was performed with the aid of a water bath with a temperature of 110 °C and 50 Hz ultrasonic and for 25 min. For the esterification reaction to synthesize biodiesel, 0.16 gm of sodium hydroxide was dissolved in 16 ml of methanol with continuous agitation for 20 min. The mixture was reacted with the lipid extract of duckweed plant and two distinct layers were obtained. FTIR and GC-MS characterisations were performed.: The FTIR results showed that the upper layer representing the ester (biodiesel) and the lower layer representing the glycerol layer. GC-MS results recorded that ester represents 69% of the ester layer, with 30.63% saturated fatty acids and 38.46% unsaturated fatty acids. These results revealed that duckweed could be a promising biomass feedstock for biodiesel production.

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1. Introduction

The dramatic increase in world population and industrialisation contribute to more demand for energy. This increase would remarkably increase the number of means of transportation, and the situation would significantly increase the demand for petroleum-based energy, especially in developed and developing countries. Statistical data demonstrated that in 2018 the global daily petroleum consumption enlarged by 1.5%, which means 1.4 million barrels. Engines with internal combustion are commonly utilized in vehicles used in transportation. Most of these engines use diesel fuel to function, emitting huge amounts of greenhouse gases (GHG) [1-4]. The emission of GHG will pollute air with poisons of carbon and nitrogen oxides and other toxic gases. To overcome this challenge, renewables are widely investigated and used as alternatives to conventional fuels. Renewable energy sources were investigated through different paths, and biomass conversion into energy products is one of these paths [5-7]. First and second generations of biofuels, ethanol, and biodiesel from plant oils, are widely explored. Therefore, biodiesel fuels produced from biomass waste, aquatic plants, and algae fatty acids are considered promising renewable energy sources [8-9].

Duckweed (*Lemna minor*) could be a viable route for the basis of biofuel production. Duckweeds are the smallest and fastest-growing flowering plants on the

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planet. All types of duckweed can grow in environments with variable pH ranging from 3.5-10.5 and a range temperature of 7–35 °C. Recent studies illustrated that the duckweeds (*Lemnaspp.*) are the most useful plants for phytoremediation compared to the other aquatic plants. These plants can efficiently absorb toxic heavy metals in addition to nitrogen and phosphorous [10-11], which offers another benefit for wastewater treatment. Verma and Suthar[12] investigated the utilization of Duckweed *Lemna* in the treatment of wastewater and the conversion of biomass of the plant into biofuel. It was concluded that the plant could be a resource of biofuel.

A large number of previous studies demonstrated that Duckweed plants can produce significant quantities of carbohydrates and other chemicals which can be converted into bioethanol or biogas [13-17]. However, fewer studies investigated the conversion of lipids of duckweeds into biodiesel. To this end, the present study aims to investigate biodiesel production from duckweed plants cultivated from wastewater plants by extracting lipids from the plants and esterification these lipids into biodiesel.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Feedstock preparation

The feedstock samples (Duckweed plants) were collected from ponds around the wastewater treatment plant. These ponds were occupied with untreated wastewater with a pH value of around 6.1. Duckweed plants are floating on the surface of the ponds. The collected plants were washed with tap water and distilled water. Then they were dried firstly in shadow and by direct solar radiation. The dried samples were ground to be a powder and ready for the extraction process.

2.2 Experimental work

For the extraction process, 1 gm of powder was taken and immersed in a solvent. The solvent was a mixture of chloroform and methanol (2:1). The used volume was 100 ml. The extraction process was performed with the assistance of ultrasonic. A water bath with a temperature of 110 °C was used to prepare the ultrasonic path. Ultrasonic had a frequency of 50 Hz. The experiment was achieved within 25 min.

When the required time was completed, extraction was stopped, and the mixture was filtered to separate the solid materials from the lipid extract. A rotary evaporator was used to separate the solvent, and the lipid was collected with 3 ml of normal hexane. For accuracy, the experiment was repeated three times. Figure 1 shows the apparatus used for the extraction in the experimental work.

Figure 1. Experimental apparatus of extraction; (A) ultrasonic bath; (B) filtration

For the esterification reaction to synthesize biodiesel, 0.16 gm of sodium hydroxide was dissolved in 16 ml of methanol with continuous agitation for 20 min. The prepared mixture was added to the lipid extract, and the new reaction mixture was fixed on a hotplate. The temperature was monitored at 62 °C with continuous agitation. After 90 min, the reaction was stopped, and the upper layer of the mixture was separated, representing the ester layer (biodiesel). Samples were taken for the tests of FTIR using Burker FTIR (Germany) and GC-MS for characterisation.

3. Results and Discussion

The diagnosis started with FTIR of the extract before the esterification reaction. Figure 2 shows the FTIR chart of the extract before the esterification. There are peaks at 2925 and 2894 cm^{-1} , which refer to the aliphatic C-H bond, confirming the presence of C-H, CH₂, and CH₃ groups. Furthermore, the Figure shows a clear peak at 1741 cm^{-1} , declaring the presence of C=O bond, the high frequency might refer to the presence of the ester carbonyl group. Moreover, it is apparent from the figure that there are apparent peaks at 1650 and 1521 cm^{-1} , confirming the availability of the C=C functional group. The figure supports the presence of C-O of ester, which is concluded from the presence of a distinct peak at 1262 cm^{-1} . The bond of C-C is confirmed due to the presence of peaks in the region 1032-1093 cm^{-1} , which refers to the stretch of C-C. The sharp peak at 804 cm^{-1} might be due to the bending of bond C=C-H.

Figure 2. FTIR spectrum of the extract of Duckweed plant

To prepare biodiesel from the extract, a transesterification reaction was performed by the reaction of sodium methoxide with the plant extract as explained in the experimental part. Two distinct layers were obtained: the upper layer representing the ester (biodiesel) and the lower layer representing the glycerol layer. Samples were taken from the two layers for the FTIR tests. The FTIR of the ester layer is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. FTIR chart of ester layer

Figure 3 shows that there are two sharp peaks in the region of 2800-2923 cm^{-1} , which clearly refers to the aliphatic C-H bond, which also appeared in the FTIR chart of the extract as demonstrated in Figure 2. This indicates the presence of C-H, CH_2 , and CH_3 groups in the ester layer, which is expected. It is apparent from Figure 3 that there is a clear peak at 1743 cm^{-1} , confirming the formation of ester and introducing a clear indication to the carbonyl group of ester. In addition to the peak appeared at 1743 cm^{-1} , there is another one at 1672 cm^{-1} which might refer to C=O group of ester with a small

shift or difference from the FTIR of the extract when there was no peak in this region. Peaks at 1459, 1519, and 1542 cm^{-1} refer to the bending of aliphatic C-H bond while the peak at 1191 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of C-O bond. Figure 3 illustrates some peaks in the region 400- 1000 cm^{-1} , which introduces additional evidence to the formation of ester or biodiesel. FTIR of the glycerol layer is demonstrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. FTIR chart of glycerol layer

It is apparent from Figure 4 that there is a broad and distinct peak at 3393 cm^{-1} and this due to the stretching of OH group in glycerol. The peak is broad and might come from the multiple OH in the compound. The Figure also shows peaks at 2942 and 2832 cm^{-1} , referring to the aliphatic C-H bond. Peaks appeared at 1078, 1032 and 1311 indicating the presence of C-O bond.

To elucidate further GC-MS device was used to analyse a sample of ester layer. The results are illustrated in Table 1

Table 1. Fatty acids available in the ester sample of Duckweed plant

No	Name fatty acid	Chemical Formula	Number of strings	R.time	Saturated acids Area%	Unsaturated acids Area%
1	Myristic acid	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{14}:0$	7.17	0.91	
2	Palmitic acid	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{16}:0$	10.83	11.43	
3	Palmitoleic acid	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{16}:1$	11.36		1.27
4	Margaric acid	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{17}:0$	13.47	11.88	
5	Stearic acid	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{18}:0$	16.47	0.72	
6	Oleic acid	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{18}:1(\text{n}9)$	17.27		3.77
7	Vaccenic acid	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{18}:1(\text{n}11)$	17.45		0.82
8	Linoleic acid	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{18}:2$	19.20		14.20
9	γ -Linolenic acid	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{18}:3(\text{n}6)$	20.52		0.79
10	α -Linolenic acid	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{18}:3(\text{n}3)$	22.06		17.60
11	Arachidic acid	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{20}:0$	24.78	5.69	
	Σ Fatty acids=69.09 SFA % = 44.33 MUFA % = 8.49 PUFA % = 47.17				30.63	38.46

4. Conclusion

Utilising aquatic plants for biofuel production support renewable energy and sustainability. Duckweed plants were subjected to an esterification process, and the FTIR GS-MS results showed that these plants have a high potential for biodiesel production. Different ester groups were detected in FTIR, and the formed ester represents 69% of the ester layer with 30.63% of saturated fatty acids and 38.46% of unsaturated fatty acids. Therefore, based on the research outcome, the study recommends increasing the cultivation of this plant for biodiesel production. As a further study, investigating the duckweed effect on the removal of pollutants from wastewater would magnify the utilisation of these plants.

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